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AGROecological strategies for SUStainable weed management in key European crops

MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH PROJECT BASED ON

Universidade de Vigo

 CSIC
CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTÍFICAS

 feuga fundación empresa universidad gallega

 UNIVERSYTET ROLNICZY
Im. Hugona Kollataja w Krakowie

 UNIVERSIDADE da MADEIRA

 UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI MILANO

 seipasa
natural technology

 MALATYA TURGUT ÖZAL UNIVERSITESI

 Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena

 UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA DE VALÈNCIA

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Agrarunternehmen Starbarch-Sachsen eG

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Liga Asociaților Producătorilor Agricoli din România

 RML
RADIOFARMISTOD LANDBUNADARINS

 SOPRONI EGYETEM

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding (Grant amount: 4 689 926.25€) from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101084084

